

SuperHyperSoft Sets Using Python and its Applications in Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets under TOPSIS Method

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Abstract: In this paper, we present an integrated framework that combines python-based implementation of SuperHyperSoft Sets (SHSSs) with a robust Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) model using Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets (NSHSSs) and the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) method. This framework is designed to address complex decision-making problems under uncertainty, vagueness and indeterminacy, particularly in academic contexts such as selecting an optimal Q1 journal for manuscript submission. The implementation constructs power sets of hierarchical sub-criteria, computes Cartesian products and generates NSHSS-based logical propositions to enable a structured and dynamic analysis. The model incorporates linguistic evaluations from multiple decision makers, converting them into Neutrosophic Sets (NSs) and computing decision-maker weights based on true (T), indeterminacy (I) and false (F) values. A case study involving the evaluation of four top-tier journals across six major criteria demonstrates the applicability and effectiveness of the proposed method. The resulting decision matrix, ideal solutions, and closeness coefficients illustrate how this approach enhances realism, sensitivity and objectivity in MCDM scenarios.

Keywords: Soft Set; Neutrosophic Set; Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Set; TOPSIS method; MCDM.

1. Introduction

Selecting an appropriate Q1 journal for publishing in mathematical sciences is a crucial decision that affects a researcher's visibility, impact and academic credibility. With numerous high-ranking journals available, choosing the right one involves evaluating various factors such as scope, impact factor, indexing, peer-review quality, acceptance rate, publication time and ethical policies. These criteria often carry different priorities based on individual researcher needs especially when under time constraints like promotions or grant applications. Given the complexity, a structured MCDM approach is necessary to compare and rank journals effectively. Techniques like TOPSIS, Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), VlseKriterijumska Optimizacija I Kompromisno Resenje (VIKOR) and Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluations (PROMETHEE) support such evaluations by assigning weights to both quantitative and qualitative criteria. Challenges such as publication cost, accessibility and alignment with a journal's scope further complicate the decision. Open access journals, for instance, often impose high Article Processing Charges (APCs) which may be unaffordable without funding. Moreover, journal reputation metrics like Impact Factor and

SCImago Rank, though useful, are insufficient alone. Ethical publishing practices and indexing in major databases (Scopus, WoS, MathSciNet, etc) also matter. This study proposes an MCDM framework using the TOPSIS method to assist researchers in mathematical sciences to select the most suitable Q1 journal for maximizing research visibility and academic success.

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides an introduction of the study.
- Section 1.1 presents a literature review for this paper under TOPSIS method.
- Section 2 introduces the preliminaries of the study using NSHSSs.
- Section 3 delivers the python coding for SHSSs which is applied in NSHSSs.
- Section 4 gives the algorithm of the NSHSSs under TOPSIS method.
- Section 5 presents the numerical example for the proposing method.
- Section 6 provides the comparison & geometric representation of the propositions.
- Section 7 gives the conclusion and results of the document.

1.1. Literature Review

Soft Set (SS) is introduced by Dmitriy Molodtsov [22] at 1999 which is used to dealing with the uncertainties in any environment. The basic operations of SS, rules for dealing the SSs and applications of SSs are used in various theories like probability, fuzzy, vague sets. The HyperSoft Set (HSS) is introduced by Smarandache [39] at 2018 which is the extension of the SSs. Later Saeed et al. [28] at 2020 released the fundamental concept and applications of the HSSs. In recent years, new type of the HSS also available in papers as intermsoft set, intermhypersoft set by Samarandache [41]. A SHSS is dealing with the Cartesian product of the power set mapping to the power set of the universal set which is introduced by Smarandache [40] at 2023.

NS is handling the uncertain information in all situations it is initiated by Smarandache [37]. The neutrosophic element is characterized by true, indeterminacy and false. Maji [20] who is alliance the neutrosophic concept into SSs which is called Neutrosophic Soft set (NSS). Neutrosophic HyperSoft Set (NHSS) [38] is expanded version of the NSS which is mostly dealing with the multiple attributes and multi- criteria problems. In recently, introducing the new concept is NSHSS [43] by Smarandache et al. at 2025 which is dealing uncertainty in SHSSs.

TOPSIS was first developed by Hwang & Yoon [14]. TOPSIS method is generally based on the classical algorithm which is used to solving the problems. It is a widely used method for solving MCDM problems [5, 7, 8, 24]. Neutrosophic TOPSIS is developed by Abdel – Basset et al. [2] which consisting the indeterminacy in problems. It is participating in the various fields such as application in personnel selection [23], OWA framework for evaluating data protection strategies in judicial systems [6], decision making using accuracy function [36] and etc. The TOPSIS method has been applied in different NSs in several application areas is tabulated below:

The Table 1 provides information on TOPSIS method which is corresponding NS extensions and their application areas.

Table 1. Neutrosophic TOPSIS in various applications

Author(s)	Type of sets	Application area
Zulqarnain et al. [47]	SSs	Decision making via soft sets
Tiwari et al. [45]	SSs	Product design concept evaluation
Dhanalakshmi & Sandhiya [11]	Fuzzy hypersoft sets	Project selection
Ramasamy et al. [26]	NSHSSs	Selecting high quality mobile phones
Smarandache et al. [42]	NSHSSs	Optimizing electric vehicle selection
Sudha et al. [44]	Plithogenic hypersoft sets	Supplier selection with different MCDM
Bobin et al. [9]	Cubic hypersoft sets	Decision making problems
Abdalla et al. [1]	Interval-valued Fermatean neutrosophic super hypersoft sets	Prioritization of patients awaiting organ transplantation
Sajid et al. [30]	Single valued neutrosophic cubic hypersoft sets	Supplier selection in the health care industry
Sajid et al. [29]	Single valued neutrosophic cubic hypersoft sets	Evaluation of motorcycle brands
Ahsan et al. [3]	Fuzzy hypersoft sets	Optimizing new technology implementation
Sajid et al. [31]	Cubic intuitionistic fuzzy hypersoft sets	Solar panel selection
Chen [10]	SHSSs	Measuring the efficiency of competitive sports talent cultivation
Kaur & Singh [18]	Neutrosophic picture hypersoft sets	MCDM
Riaz et al. [27]	Neutrosophic N-soft sets	Multiple attribute decision making

Saqlain et al. [33]	NSSs	Application of smart phone selection
Pramanik et al. [25]	NSSs	Multiple attribute decision making
Saqlain et al. [34]	NHSSs	Medical diagnosis and treatment
Jafar et al. [15]	NHSSs	Renewable energy source selection
Ajabnoor [4]	NHSSs	Evaluation of distributed leadership in education
Saqlain et al. [35]	NHSSs	Distance and similarity measures
Zulqarnain et al. [48]	NHSSs	Matrices with application to solve multi attributive decision-making problems
Fujita [12]	SHSSs	Superhyper decision-making
Zhang [46]	SHSSs	Framework for college English blended teaching quality evaluation
Liu [19]	SHSSs	Teaching quality Analysis in college English translation course

Many studies have applied the TOPSIS method to decision-making problems. In this study, we use the NSHSSs in the TOPSIS method to determine the best alternative. This method is highly effective for decision-making problems, as it accurately calculates closeness coefficient values and ranks alternatives efficiently. Here, we apply the TOPSIS method to identify the best Q1 journal for publishing mathematical research using NSHSSs.

The process includes:

1. Determining the weights of the decision-makers and these values using to finding the NSHSS aggregation values.
2. Multiplying the weights and aggregated values using the multiplication operator.
3. Calculating the separation measure for each alternative from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Positive Ideal Solution (NSHSPIS) and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Negative Ideal Solution (NSHSNIS).
4. Evaluating the Euclidean distance, it provides the accurate closeness coefficient values for the propositions.
5. Ranking the alternatives based on the closeness coefficient value.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1: [32] Let U be a universe of discourse. A NS H in U having the form $H = \{ \langle a, \rho_H(a), \sigma_H(a), \tau_H(a) \rangle : a \in U \}$ where $\rho_H(a)$, $\sigma_H(a)$ and $\tau_H(a)$ which represent the true, indeterminacy and false respectively. The mapping of the neutrosophic components are $\rho_H(a)$, $\sigma_H(a)$, $\tau_H(a): U \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $0 \leq \rho_H(a) + \sigma_H(a) + \tau_H(a) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.2: [13] Let U be a universe of discourse and $\mathfrak{P}(U)$ denote the power set of U . Consider n distinct attributes z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n where $n \geq 1$. Each attribute z_i is associated with a set of attribute values Z_i , satisfying $Z_i \cap Z_j = \emptyset$ for all $i \neq j$. Define $\mathfrak{P}(Z_i)$ is the power set of Z_i for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then the Cartesian product of the power sets of attribute value is given by $\mathfrak{C} = \mathfrak{P}(Z_1) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_2) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_3) \times \dots \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_n)$. A SHSS over U is a pair (F, C) where $F: C \rightarrow \mathfrak{P}(U)$

Definition 2.3: [43] Let U be a universe of discourse and $\mathfrak{P}(U)$ denote the power set of U . Consider n distinct attributes z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n where $n \geq 1$. Each attribute z_i is associated with a set of attribute values Z_i , satisfying $Z_i \cap Z_j = \emptyset$ for all $i \neq j$. Define $\mathfrak{P}(Z_i)$ is the power set of Z_i for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then the Cartesian product of the power sets of attribute value is given by $\mathfrak{C} = \mathfrak{P}(Z_1) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_2) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_3) \times \dots \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_n)$. A NSHSS over U as the pair (F, C) where $F: C \rightarrow \mathfrak{P}(U)$ and $F, C = \{ \gamma, \langle a, \rho_{F(\gamma)}(a), \sigma_{F(\gamma)}(a), \tau_{F(\gamma)}(a) \rangle : a \in U, \gamma \in C \subseteq Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_n \}$ where $\rho_{F(\gamma)}(a)$, $\sigma_{F(\gamma)}(a)$ & $\tau_{F(\gamma)}(a)$ represents the true, indeterminacy and false respectively. The mapping of the NSHSS components is $\rho_{F(\gamma)}(a), \sigma_{F(\gamma)}(a), \tau_{F(\gamma)}(a): U \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $0 \leq \rho_{F(\gamma)}(a) + \sigma_{F(\gamma)}(a) + \tau_{F(\gamma)}(a) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.4: [10] Let U be a universe of discourse and $\mathfrak{P}(U)$ denote the power set of U . Consider n distinct attributes z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n where $n \geq 1$. Each attribute z_i is associated with a set of attribute values Z_i , satisfying $Z_i \cap Z_j = \emptyset$ for all $i \neq j$. Define $\mathfrak{P}(Z_i)$ is the power set of Z_i for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then the Cartesian product of the power sets of attribute value is given by $\mathfrak{C} = \mathfrak{P}(Z_1) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_2) \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_3) \times \dots \times \mathfrak{P}(Z_n)$. Let α, β be two NSHSS over U is defined as pair (α, C) and (β, C) where $\alpha, \beta: C \rightarrow \mathfrak{P}(U)$ and $\alpha = \{ \gamma, \langle a, \rho_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a), \sigma_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a), \tau_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \rangle : a \in U, \gamma \in C \}$, $\beta = \{ \gamma, \langle b, \rho_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \sigma_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \tau_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) \rangle : b \in U, \gamma \in C \}$.

Then the basic operators are defined as

$$1. \alpha \oplus \beta = \langle \rho_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) + \rho_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) - \rho_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \rho_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \sigma_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \sigma_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \tau_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \tau_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) \rangle. \tag{1}$$

$$2. \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \alpha_i = \langle 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \rho_{\alpha_i(\gamma)}(a)), \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \sigma_{\alpha_i(\gamma)}(a)), \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \tau_{\alpha_i(\gamma)}(a)) \rangle. \tag{2}$$

$$3. \alpha \otimes \beta = \langle \rho_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \rho_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \sigma_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) + \sigma_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) - \sigma_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \sigma_{\beta(\gamma)}(b), \tau_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) + \tau_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) - \tau_{\alpha(\gamma)}(a) \cdot \tau_{\beta(\gamma)}(b) \rangle. \tag{3}$$

3. SHSS using python & application of NSHSSs

Python coding is used to defining the data, making the operation, create data visualizations and calculations in various situations. Here using the python coding, to get the power set of the universal set, power set of the sub-criteria, Cartesian product and propositions. Then we take the appropriate proposition for our problem thorough the result of the python coding.

The python coding is given below:

```

1. from itertools import chain, combinations, product
2. def get_valid_int(prompt):
3.     while True:
4.         try:
5.             value = int(input(prompt))
6.             return value
7.         except ValueError:
8.             print("Invalid input. Please enter an integer.")
9. def get_valid_str(prompt):
10.    while True:
11.        value = input(prompt).strip()
12.        if value:
13.            return value
14.        else:
15.            print("Invalid input. Please enter a non-empty string.")
16. def get_universe():
17.    n = get_valid_int("Enter number of elements in the universe U: ")
18.    U = []
19.    for i in range(n):
20.        elem = get_valid_str(f"Enter element {i+1} of U: ")
21.        U.append(elem)
22.    return U
23.
24. def powerset(s):
25.    return list(chain.from_iterable(combinations(s, r) for r in range(len(s)+1)))
26.
27. def get_criteria():
28.    criteria = []
29.    n_criteria = get_valid_int("Enter number of criteria: ")
30.    for i in range(n_criteria):
31.        crit_name = get_valid_str(f"Enter name for main criterion {i+1}: ")
32.        n_sub = get_valid_int(f"Enter number of sub-criteria for {crit_name}: ")
33.        sub_criteria = []
34.        for j in range(n_sub):
35.            sub_name = get_valid_str(f"Enter sub-criterion {j+1} for {crit_name}: ")
36.            sub_criteria.append(sub_name)
37.        criteria.append((crit_name, sub_criteria))
38.    return criteria
39.
40. def cartesian_product(powersets):
41.    return list(product(*powersets))
42.
43. def generate_nshss(cart_prod, power_set_U):
44.    mapping = {}
45.    for cp in cart_prod:
46.        # For demonstration: assign a subset of U based on hash

```

```

47.     mapping[cp] = power_set_U[(hash(cp) % len(power_set_U))]
48.     return mapping
49.
50. def main():
51.     print("Step 1 & 2: Get Universe Set")
52.     U = get_universe()
53.
54.     print("\nStep 3: Power Set of U")
55.     power_set_U = powerset(U)
56.     print("Power Set of U:", power_set_U)
57.
58.     print("\nStep 4 & 5: Get Criteria and Sub-Criteria")
59.     criteria = get_criteria()
60.
61.     print("\nStep 6: Power Set for Each Sub-Criterion")
62.     powersets = []
63.     for crit_name, sub_crit in criteria:
64.         ps = powerset(sub_crit)
65.         powersets.append(ps)
66.         print(f"Power Set of {crit_name}: {ps}")
67.
68.     print("\nStep 7: Cartesian Product of All Power Sets")
69.     cart_prod = cartesian_product(powersets)
70.     print(f"Total Cartesian Product combinations: {len(cart_prod)}")
71.     for idx, item in enumerate(cart_prod, 1):
72.         print(f"{idx}: {item}")
73.
74.     print("\nStep 8: SuperHyperSoft Set Mapping")
75.     nshss = generate_nshss(cart_prod, power_set_U)
76.     for k, v in nshss.items():
77.         print(f"Mapping {k} -> {v}")
78.
79.     print("\nStep 9: Number of Possible Propositions")
80.     print(f"Total Propositions: {len(cart_prod)}")
81.
82.     print("\nStep 10: All Propositions")
83.     for i, prop in enumerate(cart_prod, 1):
84.         print(f"Proposition {i}: {prop}")
85. if __name__ == "__main__":
86.     main()

```

If we give other than integer it gives the "Invalid input. Please enter an integer" which is shown below:

Step 1 & 2: Get Universe Set

Enter number of elements in the universe U: e

Invalid input. Please enter an integer.

Enter number of elements in the universe U: 4

Enter element 1 of U: A

The below figure shows the universal set and step 3 gives the power set of the universal set.

Step 1 & 2: Get Universe Set

Enter number of elements in the universe U: 4

Enter element 1 of U: A

Enter element 2 of U: B

Enter element 3 of U: C

Enter element 4 of U: D

Step 3: Power Set of U

Power Set of U: [(), ('A'), ('B'), ('C'), ('D'), ('A', 'B'), ('A', 'C'), ('A', 'D'), ('B', 'C'), ('B', 'D'), ('C', 'D'), ('A', 'B', 'C'), ('A', 'B', 'D'), ('A', 'C', 'D'), ('B', 'C', 'D'), ('A', 'B', 'C', 'D')]

The step 4 & step 5 gives the criteria and sub-criteria. If we gives the empty criteria it shows "Invalid input. Please enter a non-empty string" which shown below:

Step 4 & 5: Get Criteria and Sub-Criteria

Enter number of criteria: 2

Enter name for main criterion 1: Fruits

Enter number of sub-criteria for Fruits: 1

Enter sub-criterion 1 for Fruits:

Invalid input. Please enter a non-empty string.

Enter sub-criterion 1 for Fruits: Apple

Enter name for main criterion 2:

The below figure shows the criteria and sub-criteria:

Step 4 & 5: Get Criteria and Sub-Criteria

Enter number of criteria: 2

Enter name for main criterion 1: Fruits

Enter number of sub-criteria for Fruits: 2

Enter sub-criterion 1 for Fruits: Apple

Enter sub-criterion 2 for Fruits: Orange

Enter name for main criterion 2: Vegetables

Enter number of sub-criteria for Vegetables: 3

Enter sub-criterion 1 for Vegetables: Carrot

Enter sub-criterion 2 for Vegetables: Beans

Enter sub-criterion 3 for Vegetables: potato

Given the criteria details, step 6 generates the power set of the each criteria which shows the below:

Step 6: Power Set for Each Sub-Criterion

Power Set of Fruits: [(), ('Apple'), ('Orange'), ('Apple', 'Orange')]

Power Set of Vegetables: [(), ('Carrot'), ('Beans'), ('potato'), ('Carrot', 'Beans'), ('Carrot', 'potato'), ('Beans', 'potato'), ('Carrot', 'Beans', 'potato')]

Step 7 delivers the Cartesian product of the criteria & sub-criteria.

Step 7: Cartesian Product of All Power Sets

Total Cartesian Product combinations: 32

- 1: ((), ())
- 2: ((), ('Carrot',))
- 3: ((), ('Beans',))
- 4: ((), ('potato',))
- 5: ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans'))
- 6: ((), ('Carrot', 'potato'))
- 7: ((), ('Beans', 'potato'))
- 8: ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans', 'potato'))
- 9: (('Apple',), ())
- 10: (('Apple',), ('Carrot',))
- 11: (('Apple',), ('Beans',))
- 12: (('Apple',), ('potato',))
- 13: (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'Beans'))
- 14: (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'potato'))
- 15: (('Apple',), ('Beans', 'potato'))
- 16: (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'Beans', 'potato'))
- 17: (('Orange',), ())
- 18: (('Orange',), ('Carrot',))

Here we give the 18 Cartesian product values, similarly finding the remaining values. Step 8 given NSHSS mapping which is shown below:

Step 8: Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Set Mapping

- Mapping ((), ()) -> ('A', 'C')
- Mapping ((), ('Carrot',)) -> ('C',)
- Mapping ((), ('Beans',)) -> ('A', 'B')
- Mapping ((), ('Potato',)) -> ('C',)
- Mapping ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans')) -> ('B', 'D')
- Mapping ((), ('Carrot', 'Potato')) -> ('A', 'D')
- Mapping ((), ('Beans', 'Potato')) -> ('D',)
- Mapping ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans', 'Potato')) -> ('A', 'B')
- Mapping (('Apple',), ()) -> ('A', 'B')
- Mapping (('Apple',), ('Carrot',)) -> ('B',)
- Mapping (('Apple',), ('Beans',)) -> ('D',)
- Mapping (('Apple',), ('Potato',)) -> ('B',)
- Mapping (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'Beans')) -> ('B', 'C')
- Mapping (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'Potato')) -> ('A', 'C')

Step 9 gives the number of total propositions of criteria and sub-criteria. Step 10 given the 15 propositions out of 32 propositions. Similarly, find the all other propositions.

Step 9: Number of Possible Propositions

Total Propositions: 32

Step 10: All Propositions

Proposition 1: ((), ())

Proposition 2: ((), ('Carrot',))

Proposition 3: ((), ('Beans',))

Proposition 4: ((), ('potato',))

Proposition 5: ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans'))

Proposition 6: ((), ('Carrot', 'potato'))

Proposition 7: ((), ('Beans', 'potato'))

Proposition 8: ((), ('Carrot', 'Beans', 'potato'))

Proposition 9: (('Apple',), ())

Proposition 10: (('Apple',), ('Carrot',))

Proposition 11: (('Apple',), ('Beans',))

Proposition 12: (('Apple',), ('potato',))

Proposition 13: (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'Beans'))

Proposition 14: (('Apple',), ('Carrot', 'potato'))

Proposition 15: (('Apple',), ('Beans', 'potato'))

4. Algorithm for NSHSSs in MCDM problem under TOPSIS method**Step 1:** Start the process.

Consider the MCDM problem with alternatives, criteria, sub-criteria and decision makers.

Let $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_m\}$ be the set of alternatives, $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n\}$ be the set of criteria, $\{Q_{1.1..n}, Q_{2.1..n}, \dots, Q_{n.1..n}\}$ be the set of sub-criteria and $L = \{L_1, L_2, \dots, L_p\}$ be the set of decision makers.**Step 2:** Choosing the propositions by using the criteria and sub-criteria in NSHSS.**Step 3:** Calculating the importance of decision makers using linguistic table. We have a p decision makers and $L_t = (\rho_t, \sigma_t, \tau_t)$ where $t=1, 2, \dots, p$.

$$\text{Weight of the decision makers } L_t = \frac{\rho_t + \sigma_t \left(\frac{\rho_t}{\rho_t + \tau_t} \right)}{\sum_{t=1}^p \rho_t + \sigma_t \left(\frac{\rho_t}{\rho_t + \tau_t} \right)} \quad (4)$$

and $\sum_{t=1}^p L_t = 1$.**Step 4:** Constructed the decision value of the preposition with NSHSS which contains the true, indeterminacy and false membership value.**Step 5:** Finding the aggregated neutrosophic decision value based on the decision makers. Here we have a 'm' alternatives and 'n' criteria then using the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Weighted Averaging (NSHSSWA) aggregation operator as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= (e_{ij})_{m \times n} = \text{NSHSSWA}_L \left(e_{ij}^{(1)}, e_{ij}^{(2)}, \dots, e_{ij}^{(p)} \right) \\ &= L_1 e_{ij}^{(1)} \oplus L_2 e_{ij}^{(2)}, \dots, \oplus L_p e_{ij}^{(p)} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \langle 1 - \prod_{t=1}^p (1 - \rho_{ij}^{(p)})^{L_t}, \prod_{t=1}^p (\sigma_{ij}^{(p)})^{L_t}, \prod_{t=1}^p (\tau_{ij}^{(p)})^{L_t} \rangle \tag{5}$$

where $e_{ij} = \langle \rho_{ij}, \sigma_{ij}, \tau_{ij} \rangle$ is aggregated element of E for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Step 6: Finding the weights of the criteria using NSHSSWA aggregation operator as follows

$$\begin{aligned} O = o_j &= NSHSSWA_L(o_j^{(1)}, o_j^{(2)}, \dots, o_j^{(p)}) \\ &= L_1 o_j^{(1)} \oplus L_2 o_j^{(2)} \dots \oplus L_p o_j^{(p)} \\ &= \langle 1 - \prod_{t=1}^p (1 - \rho_j^{(p)})^{L_t}, \prod_{t=1}^p (\sigma_j^{(p)})^{L_t}, \prod_{t=1}^p (\tau_j^{(p)})^{L_t} \rangle. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$O = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n\}$ and $o_j = \langle \rho_j, \sigma_j, \tau_j \rangle$ for $j=1, 2, \dots, n$.

Step 7: Calculate the weighted aggregated value using the multiplication operator.

$E \otimes O = E^o = \langle e_{ij}^{o_j} \rangle_{m \times n} = \langle \rho_{ij}^{o_j}, \sigma_{ij}^{o_j}, \tau_{ij}^{o_j} \rangle_{m \times n}$ where ' E ' denotes the aggregated decision value and ' O ' denotes the weights of the criteria.

Step 8: The Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and the Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) is follows as:

$$\begin{aligned} PIS = W^+ &= \{e_1^+, e_2^+, \dots, e_n^+\} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\max_j e_{ij} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\min_j e_{ij} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \mid j = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} NIS = W^- &= \{e_1^-, e_2^-, \dots, e_n^-\} \\ &= \left\{ \left(\min_j e_{ij} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\max_j e_{ij} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \mid j = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\} \end{aligned}$$

where R_1 and R_2 the benefit and cost-type criteria respectively.

Now we determine the NSHSNIS and NSHSPIS using the following:

$$W^+ = [e_1^{o+}, e_2^{o+}, \dots, e_n^{o+}] \tag{7}$$

where $e_j^{o+} = \langle \rho_j^{o+}, \sigma_j^{o+}, \tau_j^{o+} \rangle$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

$$\rho_j^{o+} = \left\{ \left(\max_i \{ \rho_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\min_i \{ \rho_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

$$\sigma_j^{o+} = \left\{ \left(\min_i \{ \sigma_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\max_i \{ \sigma_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

$$\tau_j^{o+} = \left\{ \left(\min_i \{ \tau_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\max_i \{ \tau_{ij}^{o_j} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

and

$$W^- = [e_1^{o-}, e_2^{o-}, \dots, e_n^{o-}] \tag{8}$$

where $e_j^{o-} = \langle \rho_j^{o-}, \sigma_j^{o-}, \tau_j^{o-} \rangle$ for $j=1, 2, \dots, n$.

$$\rho_j^{o-} = \left\{ \left(\min_i \{ \rho_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\max_i \{ \rho_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

$$\sigma_j^{o-} = \left\{ \left(\max_i \{ \sigma_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\min_i \{ \sigma_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

$$\tau_j^{o-} = \left\{ \left(\max_i \{ \tau_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_1 \right), \left(\min_i \{ \tau_{ij}^{oj} \} \mid j \in R_2 \right) \right\}.$$

Step 9: (Euclidean distance) Let U be a universe of discourse and $l \in U$. Let $X = \{(a_1 | \langle \rho_X(a_1), \sigma_X(a_1), \tau_X(a_1) \rangle), \dots, (a_n | \langle \rho_X(a_n), \sigma_X(a_n), \tau_X(a_n) \rangle)\}$ and $Y = \{(a_1 | \langle \rho_Y(a_1), \sigma_Y(a_1), \tau_Y(a_1) \rangle), \dots, (a_n | \langle \rho_Y(a_n), \sigma_Y(a_n), \tau_Y(a_n) \rangle)\}$ be two NSHSSs for $a_i \in U (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$. Then the Euclidean distance between two NSHSSs α and β can be defined as follows:

$$\aleph(\alpha, \beta) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \left\{ \left(\rho_\alpha(a_i) - \rho_\beta(a_i) \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_\alpha(a_i) - \sigma_\beta(a_i) \right)^2 + \left(\tau_\alpha(a_i) - \tau_\beta(a_i) \right)^2 \right\}}.$$

Using the above equation to calculating the Euclidean measure of NSHSS from NSHSPIS and NSHSNIS,

Euclidean distance of each alternative $\langle \rho_{ij}^{oj}, \sigma_{ij}^{oj}, \tau_{ij}^{oj} \rangle$ from NSHSPIS $\langle \rho_{ij}^{o+}, \sigma_{ij}^{o+}, \tau_{ij}^{o+} \rangle$ written as:

$$\aleph^{i+} \left(e_{ij}^{oj}, e_j^{o+} \right) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \left\{ \left(\rho_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \rho_{ij}^{o+}(a_j) \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \sigma_{ij}^{o+}(a_j) \right)^2 + \left(\tau_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \tau_{ij}^{o+}(a_j) \right)^2 \right\}}. \tag{9}$$

Euclidean distance of each alternative $\langle \rho_{ij}^{oj}, \sigma_{ij}^{oj}, \tau_{ij}^{oj} \rangle$ from NSHSNIS $\langle \rho_{ij}^{o-}, \sigma_{ij}^{o-}, \tau_{ij}^{o-} \rangle$ written as:

$$\aleph^{i-} \left(e_{ij}^{oj}, e_j^{o-} \right) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \left\{ \left(\rho_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \rho_{ij}^{o-}(a_j) \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \sigma_{ij}^{o-}(a_j) \right)^2 + \left(\tau_{ij}^{oj}(a_j) - \tau_{ij}^{o-}(a_j) \right)^2 \right\}}. \tag{10}$$

Step 10: Using the Euclidean distance to finding the closeness coefficient and ranking the alternatives through the closeness coefficient,

$$\nabla_i = \frac{\aleph^{i-}(e_{ij}^{oj}, e_j^-)}{\aleph^{i+}(e_{ij}^{oj}, e_j^+) + \aleph^{i-}(e_{ij}^{oj}, e_j^-)} \text{ where } 0 \leq \nabla_i \leq 1. \tag{11}$$

Step 11: End the process.

The figure 1 shows the simple visualization of the TOPSIS method which is given below.

5. Numerical example

Step 1:

The researcher is considering four Q1-ranked mathematical journals

Journal 1 (Γ_{10}), Journal 2 (Γ_{11}), Journal 3 (Γ_{12}), Journal 4 (Γ_{13}).

Here criteria and sub-criteria for journal selection which have six main criteria with relevant sub-criteria as follows:

Figure 1. TOPSIS algorithm representation

1. Journal Impact & Ranking (JIR)

JIR-1: Impact Factor (IF) and h-index.

JIR-2: SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) and Quartile (Q1 in Scopus/WoS).

JIR-3: Average Citations per Paper in the Last 5 Years.

2. Peer-Review & Acceptance Process (PAP)

PAP-1: Quality of Peer-Review Process (Double-Blind, Single-Blind, Open).

PAP-2: Average Review Time (weeks/months).

PAP-3: Acceptance Rate (%).

3. Scope & Specialization (SP)

SP-1: Relevance to the Research Area (Pure & Applied Mathematics, etc.).

SP-2: Special Issues or Thematic Sections Related to Research Topic.

SP-3: Editorial Board’s Reputation and Expertise in the Field.

4. Publication Costs & Open Access (PCOA)

PCOA-1: Article Processing Charges (APC) for Open Access.

PCOA-2: Subscription-Based or Hybrid Model (Open Access Option).

PCOA-3: Institutional Discounts, Fee Waivers, or Funding Support Availability.

5. Visibility & Indexing (VI)

VI-1: Inclusion in Major Databases (SCOPUS, Web of Science, MathSciNet, Zentralblatt MATH).

VI-2: Readership, University Subscriptions, and Citation Visibility.

6. Ethical & Editorial Policies (EEP)

EEP-1: Compliance with COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) Guidelines.

EEP-2: Plagiarism Detection, Retraction Policies, and Ethical Standards.

The figure 2 shows the criteria and sub-criteria of journal selection. This shows the mainly 6 criteria such as JIR, PAP, SP, PCOA, VI and the EEP. The first 4 criteria have the 3 sub-criteria and the last 2 criteria have 2 sub-criteria.

Step 2:

SHSSs in criteria

Here we using the section 3 (python coding for SHSSs) which is help to finding the power set of universal set and criteria, Cartesian product and propositions.

The power set of JIR is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{JIR})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{JIR}) = \{\emptyset, \{\text{JIR-1}\}, \{\text{JIR-2}\}, \{\text{JIR-3}\}, \{\text{JIR-1}, \text{JIR-2}\}, \{\text{JIR-1}, \text{JIR-3}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{JIR-1}, \text{JIR-2}, \text{JIR-3}\}, \{\text{JIR-2}, \text{JIR-3}\}\}$. The power set of PAP is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PAP})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PAP}) = \{\emptyset, \{\text{PAP-1}\}, \{\text{PAP-2}\}, \{\text{PAP-3}\}, \{\text{PAP-1}, \text{PAP-2}\}, \{\text{PAP-2}, \text{PAP-3}\}, \{\text{PAP-1}, \text{PAP-3}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{PAP-1}, \text{PAP-2}, \text{PAP-3}\}\}$. The power set of SP is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{SP})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{SP}) = \{\emptyset, \{\text{SP-1}\}, \{\text{SP-2}\}, \{\text{SP-3}\}, \{\text{SP-1}, \text{SP-2}\}, \{\text{SP-2}, \text{SP-3}\}, \{\text{SP-1}, \text{SP-3}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{SP-1}, \text{SP-2}, \text{SP-3}\}\}$. The power set of PCOA is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PCOA})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PCOA}) = \{\emptyset, \{\text{PCOA-1}\}, \{\text{PCOA-2}\}, \{\text{PCOA-3}\}, \{\text{PCOA-1}, \text{PCOA-2}\}, \{\text{PCOA-1}, \text{PCOA-3}\}, \{\text{PCOA-2}, \text{PCOA-3}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{PCOA-1}, \text{PCOA-2}, \text{PCOA-3}\}\}$. The power set of VI is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{VI})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{VI}) = \{\{\emptyset, \{\text{VI-1}\}, \{\text{VI-2}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{VI-1}, \text{VI-2}\}\}\}$. The power set of EEP is denoted by $\mathfrak{P}(\text{EEP})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{EEP}) = \{\{\emptyset, \{\text{EEP-1}\}, \{\text{EEP-2}\}, \{\emptyset, \text{EEP-1}, \text{EEP-2}\}\}\}$.

The power set of U is denoted $\mathfrak{P}(U)$ and $\mathfrak{P}(U) = \{\emptyset, \{\Gamma_{10}\}, \{\Gamma_{11}\}, \{\Gamma_{12}\}, \{\Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{12}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{12}\}, \{\Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{12}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{12}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{12}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{12}, \Gamma_{13}\}, \{\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{12}, \Gamma_{13}\}\}$.

Here we select the one best Q1 journal among the four journals so we considering the single element as alternatives.

Alternatives = $\{\Gamma_{10}\}, \{\Gamma_{11}\}, \{\Gamma_{12}\}, \{\Gamma_{13}\}$.

The SHSS is $F: \mathfrak{P}(\text{JIR}) \times \mathfrak{P}(\text{PAP}) \times \mathfrak{P}(\text{SP}) \times \mathfrak{P}(\text{PCOA}) \times \mathfrak{P}(\text{VI}) \times \mathfrak{P}(\text{EEP}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{P}(U)$. Here \times denotes the Cartesian product of the equation. The Cartesian product of $\mathfrak{P}(\text{JIR})$, $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PAP})$, $\mathfrak{P}(\text{SP})$, $\mathfrak{P}(\text{PCOA})$, $\mathfrak{P}(\text{VI})$ and $\mathfrak{P}(\text{EEP})$ has 65,536 elements.

Figure 2. Criteria and sub-criteria

$\mathcal{P}(\text{JIR}) \times \mathcal{P}(\text{PAP}) \times \mathcal{P}(\text{SP}) \times \mathcal{P}(\text{PCOA}) \times \mathcal{P}(\text{VI}) \times \mathcal{P}(\text{EEP}) = \{(\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PCOA} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PCOA} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PCOA} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{VI} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{VI} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{EEP} - 1\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{EEP} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 1, \text{JIR} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 1, \text{JIR} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{JIR} - 1, \text{JIR} - 2, \text{JIR} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 1, \text{PAP} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 2, \text{PAP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PAP} - 1, \text{PAP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 1, \text{SP} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 2, \text{SP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{SP} - 1, \text{SP} - 3\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{PCOA} - 1, \text{PCOA} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{VI} - 1, \text{VI} - 2\}), (\emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset, \{\text{EEP} - 1, \text{EEP} - 2\}), \text{etc...}\}$

The total combinations (propositions) is $3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2 \times 2 = 324$. Some example as follows:

Each proposition represents unique combination of the above sets.

Proposition 1: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-1, EEP-1)

Proposition 2: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-1, EEP-2)

Proposition 3: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-2, EEP-1)

Proposition 4: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-2, EEP-2)

Proposition 5: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-2, EEP-2)

Proposition 6: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-2, VI-1, EEP-1)

Proposition 7: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-2, VI-1, EEP-2)

Proposition 8: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-2, VI-2, EEP-1)

Proposition 9: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-2, VI-2, EEP-2)

Proposition 10: (JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-3, VI-1, EEP-1)

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Proposition 320: (JIR-3, PAP-2, SP-3, PCOA-2, VI-2, EEP-2)

Proposition 321: (JIR-3, PAP-2, SP-3, PCOA-3, VI-1, EEP-1)

Proposition 322: (JIR-3, PAP-2, SP-3, PCOA-3, VI-1, EEP-2)

Proposition 323: (JIR-3, PAP-2, SP-3, PCOA-3, VI-2, EEP-1)

Proposition 324: (JIR-3, PAP-2, SP-3, PCOA-3, VI-2, EEP-2).

The alternatives were assessed by decision-makers based on expert evaluations, as outlined in the below table. This table facilitates the use of linguistic variables for evaluating alternatives with respect to specific criteria. Furthermore, it provides a framework for converting the linguistic inputs from experts into NSs.

Table 2. Linguistic terms and values

Linguistic term	Notations	(ρ, σ, τ)
Extremely Weak	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 11}$	(0.000, 0.986, 0.974)
Very Weak	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 10}$	(0.108, 0.887, 0.875)
Weak	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 9}$	(0.208, 0.788, 0.776)
Slightly Weak	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 8}$	(0.308, 0.689, 0.677)
Below Average	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 7}$	(0.408, 0.590, 0.578)
Average	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 6}$	(0.508, 0.491, 0.479)
Above Average	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 5}$	(0.608, 0.392, 0.380)
Slightly Strong	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 4}$	(0.708, 0.293, 0.281)
Strong	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 3}$	(0.808, 0.194, 0.182)
Very Strong	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 2}$	(0.908, 0.095, 0.083)
Extremely Strong	$\mathfrak{N}_{\exists 1}$	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)

Here we take the four decision makers represented as $\epsilon_{AA}, \epsilon_{BB}, \epsilon_{CC}, \epsilon_{DD}$ for each decision makers have the criteria ad sub-criteria. We already choose the six criteria namely JIR, PAP, SP, PCOA, VI and EEP and the sub-criteria denoted as JIR-1, JIR-2, JIR-3, PAP-1, PAP-2, PAP-3, SP-1, SP-2,SP-3, PCOA-1, PCOA-2, PCOA-3, VI-1, VI-2 and EEP-1,EEP-2. Each Journal had the criteria, sub –criteria and the decision makers. The above information is tabulated in the Table 3.

Table 3. Decision values in linguistic terms

DM	Criteria	Sub-criteria	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}	
ϵ_{AA}	JIR	JIR-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		JIR-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		JIR-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	PAP	PAP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
		PAP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		PAP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	SP	SP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		SP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
		SP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	PCOA	PCOA-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		PCOA-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		PCOA-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	VI	VI-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		VI-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
	EEP	EEP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		EEP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
	ϵ_{BB}	JIR	JIR-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
			JIR-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
JIR-3			$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
PAP		PAP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		PAP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		PAP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
SP		SP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
		SP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
		SP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
PCOA		PCOA-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		PCOA-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		PCOA-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	

	VI	VI-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		VI-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	EEP	EEP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		EEP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
ϵ_{cc}	JIR	JIR-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		JIR-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		JIR-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
	PAP	PAP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		PAP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		PAP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
	SP	SP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		SP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		SP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	PCOA	PCOA-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
		PCOA-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		PCOA-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	
	VI	VI-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
		VI-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
	EEP	EEP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		EEP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
	ϵ_{DD}	JIR	JIR-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
			JIR-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
			JIR-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$
		PAP	PAP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$
PAP-2			$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
PAP-3			$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
SP		SP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		SP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		SP-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
PCOA		PCOA-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		PCOA-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	
		PCOA-3	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	
VI		VI-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		VI-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	
EEP		EEP-1	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	
		EEP-2	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	

Here we take 2 common propositions out of 324 propositions.

- **Proposition 1:** JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-1, EEP-2.

- **Proposition 2:** JIR-1, PAP-1, SP-1, PCOA-1, VI-1, EEP-1.

Step 3:

The Table 4 shows the importance of the decision makers which is described in the linguistic terms. The decision makers $\epsilon_{AA}, \epsilon_{BB}, \epsilon_{CC}, \epsilon_{DD}$ are described as extremely strong, very strong, strong and very strong respectively.

Table 4. Importance of the decision makers

DMs	ϵ_{AA}	ϵ_{BB}	ϵ_{CC}	ϵ_{DD}
Linguistic term	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
Linguistic value	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.908, 0.095, 0.083)	(0.808, 0.194, 0.182)	(0.908, 0.095, 0.083)

Here we have to finding the weight of the decision makers. The weights of the decision makers $\epsilon_{AA}, \epsilon_{BB}, \epsilon_{CC}, \epsilon_{DD}$ are denoted as L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4 respectively.

Using the equation (4),

$$L_1 = \frac{1+0(\frac{1}{1+0})}{(1+0(\frac{1}{1+0}))+(0.908+0.095(\frac{0.908}{0.908+0.083}))+(0.808+0.194(\frac{0.808}{0.908+0.182}))+(0.908+0.095(\frac{0.908}{0.908+0.083}))}$$

$$= \frac{1}{1+(0.908+0.095(0.916))+(0.808+0.194(0.741))+(0.908+0.095(0.916))}$$

$$= \frac{1}{1+(0.908+0.087)+(0.808+0.143)+(0.908+0.087)} = \frac{1}{1+0.995+0.951+0.995} = 0.253.$$

Similarly, we proceeding the other weight of the decision makers and get $L_2 = 0.252, L_3 = 0.244, L_4 = 0.252$.

Step 4:

Proposition 1

First we take the proposition 1, by using the TOPSIS method then finding the ranking of the journals. Table 5 represents the decision values in the linguistic notation for the proposition 1 as follows:

Table 5. Decision values in linguistic notation for proposition 1

Journals	DM	JIR-1	PAP-1	SP-1	PCOA-1	VI-1	EEP-2
Γ_{10}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
Γ_{11}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$

	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
Γ_{12}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
Γ_{13}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
Weights	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$

Step 5:

The Table 6 shows the aggregated neutrosophic value which is calculated from the equation (5) and tabulated the values below:

Table 6. Aggregated neutrosophic value

Journal/ Criteria	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.840, 0.162, 0.148)	(0.853, 0.149, 0.136)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.640, 0.251)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.853, 0.149, 0.136)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.851, 0.151, 0.137)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-2	(0.851, 0.151, 0.136)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.866, 0.130, 0.123)	(0.801, 0.200, 0.187)

By using the equation (5),

$$\rho_{11} = 1 - ((1 - 1)^{0.253} \times (1 - 0.908)^{0.252} \times (1 - 1)^{0.244} \times (1 - 1)^{0.252}) = 1.$$

$$\sigma_{11} = 0^{0.253} \times 0.095^{0.252} \times 0^{0.244} \times 0^{0.252} = 0.$$

$$\tau_{11} = 0^{0.253} \times 0.083^{0.252} \times 0^{0.244} \times 0^{0.252} = 0.$$

Consider,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{15} &= 1 - ((1 - 0.708)^{0.253} \times (1 - 0.808)^{0.252} \times (1 - 0.908)^{0.244} \times (1 - 0.908)^{0.252}) \\ &= 1 - (0.732 \times 0.659 \times 0.558 \times 0.54) = 1 - 0.149 = 0.851. \end{aligned}$$

$$\sigma_{15} = 0.293^{0.253} \times 0.194^{0.252} \times 0.095^{0.244} \times 0.095^{0.252} = 0.733 \times 0.661 \times 0.563 \times 0.5 = 0.151.$$

$$\tau_{15} = 0.281^{0.253} \times 0.182^{0.252} \times 0.083^{0.244} \times 0.083^{0.252} = 0.725 \times 0.650 \times 0.544 \times 0 = 0.136.$$

Similarly, we can find the all table values.

Step 6: The below table shows the weights of the proposition 1.

Table 7. Weights of the proposition 1

Criteria	Weights
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.840, 0.161, 0.149)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-2	(0.851, 0.151, 0.157)

The weights of the criteria as $\sigma_j = (\rho_j, \sigma_j, \tau_j)$ and using the equation (8) as follows:

Consider the weight of the PAP-1 is,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_2 &= 1 - ((1 - 0.908)^{0.253} \times (1 - 0.808)^{0.252} \times (1 - 0.808)^{0.244} \times (1 - 0.808)^{0.252}) \\ &= 1 - (0.546 \times 0.659 \times 0.668 \times 0.659) = 0.840. \end{aligned}$$

$$\sigma_2 = 0.095^{0.253} \times 0.194^{0.252} \times 0.194^{0.244} \times 0.194^{0.252} = 0.551 \times 0.661 \times 0.670 \times 0.66 = 0.161.$$

$$\tau_2 = 0.083^{0.253} \times 0.182^{0.252} \times 0.182^{0.244} \times 0.182^{0.252} = 0.532 \times 0.650 \times 0.659 \times 0.65 = 0.149.$$

Similarly, we can find all other table values.

Step 7:

Table 8. Aggregated weight neutrosophic value

Journal/Criteria	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.840, 0.161, 0.149)	(0.706, 0.298, 0.275)	(0.717, 0.287, 0.265)	(0.840, 0.161, 0.149)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.264, 0.251)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.853, 0.149, 0.136)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.851, 0.151, 0.137)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-2	(0.725, 0.279, 0.256)	(0.851, 0.151, 0.136)	(0.738, 0.266, 0.243)	(0.682, 0.321, 0.298)

The weight of the proposition 1 is using the multiplication operator in equation (3) to get $O = (1.000, 0.000, 0.000)$. Then aggregated weight neutrosophic value is calculated as follows:

$$\langle \rho_{11}^o, \sigma_{11}^o, \tau_{11}^o \rangle = \langle 1 \times 1, 0 + 0 - 0 \times 0, 0 + 0 - 0 \times 0 \rangle = \langle 1.000, 0.000, 0.000 \rangle.$$

$$\langle \rho_{12}^o, \sigma_{12}^o, \tau_{12}^o \rangle = \langle 1 \times 0.840, 0 + 0.161 - 0 \times 0.161, 0 + 0.149 - 0 \times 0.149 \rangle = \langle 0.840, 0.161, 0.149 \rangle.$$

Step 8:

Table 9. NSHSPIS and NSHSNIS

Criteria	NSHSPIS	NSHSNIS
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.840, 0.161, 0.149)	(0.706, 0.298, 0.275)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.264, 0.251)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.851, 0.151, 0.137)
EEP-2	(0.851, 0.151, 0.137)	(0.682, 0.321, 0.298)

The NSHSPIS using the equation (7), $e_1^{o+} = \langle \rho_1^{o+}, \sigma_1^{o+}, \tau_1^{o+} \rangle$ as calculated as

$$\rho_1^{o+} = \max(1.000, 1.000, 1.000, 1.000) = 1.000, \quad \sigma_1^{o+} = \min(0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000) = 0.000, \quad \tau_1^{o+} = \min(0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000) = 0.000.$$

The NSHSNIS using the equation (8), $e_1^{o-} = \langle \rho_1^{o-}, \sigma_1^{o-}, \tau_1^{o-} \rangle$ as calculated as

$$\rho_1^{o-} = \min(1.000, 1.000, 1.000, 1.000) = 1.000, \quad \sigma_1^{o-} = \max(0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000) = 0.000, \quad \tau_1^{o-} = \max(0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000) = 0.000.$$

Step 9:

Using the equation (9) & (10) we get the Euclidean distance using NSHSPIS and NSHSNIS values shown below:

Table 10. Euclidean distance from NSHSPIS & NSHSNIS

Journals	Euclidean distance using NSHSPIS	Euclidean distance using NSHSNIS
Γ_{10}	0.212	0.562
Γ_{11}	0.504	0.383
Γ_{12}	0.381	0.459
Γ_{13}	0.382	0.394

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Using the equation (9), } \aleph^{1+} &= \sqrt{\frac{\{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(0.840 - 0.840)^2 + (0.161 - 0.161)^2 + (0.149 - 0.149)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(0.725 - 0.851)^2 + (0.279 - 0.151)^2 + (0.256 - 0.137)^2\}}{\{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0.015 + 0.016 + 0.014\}} = \sqrt{0.045} = 0.212. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Using the equation (10), } \aleph^{1-} &= \sqrt{\frac{\{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(0.840 - 0.706)^2 + (0.161 - 0.298)^2 + (0.149 - 0.275)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 1.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2 + (0.000 - 0.000)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 0.731)^2 + (0.000 - 0.264)^2 + (0.000 - 0.251)^2\} + \{(1.000 - 0.851)^2 + (0.000 - 0.151)^2 + (0.000 - 0.137)^2\} + \{(0.725 - 0.682)^2 + (0.279 - 0.321)^2 + (0.256 - 0.298)^2\}}{\{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0.017 + 0.018 + 0.015\} + \{0 + 0 + 0\} + \{0.069 + 0.069 + 0.063\} + \{0.022 + 0.022 + 0.018\} + \{0.001 + 0.001 + 0.001\}} = \sqrt{0 + 0.05 + 0 + 0.201 + 0.062 + 0.03} = \sqrt{0.316} = 0.562. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can find the all other table values.

Figure 3. Euclidean distance of proposition 1

The above figure shows the comparison of the Euclidean positive ideal solution and the negative ideal solution. Here the blue line represents the positive values and orange lines represent the negative values. The 1, 2, 3, 4 represents the journals $\Gamma_{10}, \Gamma_{11}, \Gamma_{12}, \Gamma_{13}$ respectively.

Step 10:

Table 11. Closeness coefficient & ranking

Journals	Closeness Coefficient	Ranking
Γ_{10}	0.726	1
Γ_{11}	0.432	4
Γ_{12}	0.546	2
Γ_{13}	0.508	3

Using the equation (11),

$$\text{Closeness coefficient of } \Gamma_{10} \text{ is } \nabla_1 = \frac{0.562}{0.212+0.562} = \frac{0.562}{0.774} = 0.726.$$

Similarly, we can find the other journals closeness coefficients.

Ranking: $\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$.

We are taking the proposition 1 and successfully applying the algorithm of NSHSSs in MCDM problem under TOPSIS method. According to the ranking results journal Γ_{10} is the best among other 3 journals.

Step 11: End the process.

Proposition 2

Taking the proposition 2 and applying the above steps like the proposition 1 and get the closeness coefficient values then ranking the alternatives.

Table 12. Decision value in linguistic notation for proposition 2

Journals	DM	JIR-1	PAP-1	SP-1	PCOA-1	VI-1	EEP-1
Γ_{10}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$
Γ_{11}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
Γ_{12}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$
Γ_{13}	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
Weights	ϵ_{AA}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$
	ϵ_{BB}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 5}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$
	ϵ_{CC}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$
	ϵ_{DD}	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 3}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 4}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 1}$	$\mathfrak{M}_{\exists 2}$

Table 13. Aggregated neutrosophic value

Journal/ Criteria	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.841, 0.162, 0.148)	(0.852, 0.150, 0.136)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.264, 0.252)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.853, 0.150, 0.136)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.852, 0.151, 0.138)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.869, 0.134, 0.120)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.889, 0.114, 0.101)

Table 14. Weight values of the criteria for proposition 2

Criteria	Weights
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.840, 0.161, 0.149)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-1	(0.853, 0.149, 0.136)

Table15. Aggregated weight neutrosophic value

Journal/ Criteria	Γ_{10}	Γ_{11}	Γ_{12}	Γ_{13}
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.841, 0.162, 0.149)	(0.707, 0.298, 0.275)	(0.717, 0.287, 0.265)	(0.841, 0.169, 0.149)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.264, 0.252)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.853, 0.150, 0.136)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.852, 0.151, 0.138)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
EEP-1	(0.853, 0.150, 0.136)	(0.741, 0.264, 0.240)	(0.853, 0.150, 0.136)	(0.759, 0.246, 0.224)

Table 16. NSHSPIS and NSHSNIS

Criteria	NSHSPIS	NSHSNIS
JIR-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PAP-1	(0.841, 0.162, 0.194)	(0.707, 0.298, 0.275)
SP-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)
PCOA-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.737, 0.264, 0.252)
VI-1	(1.000, 0.000, 0.000)	(0.852, 0.151, 0.138)
EEP-1	(0.853, 0.150, 0.136)	(0.741, 0.264, 0.240)

Table 17. Euclidean distances from NSHSPIS & NSHSNIS

Journals	Euclidean distance using NSHSPIS	Euclidean distance using NSHSNIS
Γ_{10}	0.000	0.595
Γ_{11}	0.539	0.252
Γ_{12}	0.328	0.488
Γ_{13}	0.297	0.395

Figure 4. Euclidean distances of proposition 2

The bar diagram shows the values of the Euclidean positive & negative ideal solution of the preposition 2 which is helps to identifying the difference of distances. The 1, 2, 3, 4 shows the journals Γ_{10} , Γ_{11} , Γ_{12} , Γ_{13} respectively. The blue bar is positive Euclidean values and orange is negative Euclidean values.

Table 18. Closeness coefficient & ranking

Journals	Closeness coefficient	Ranking
Γ_{10}	1.000	1
Γ_{11}	0.318	4
Γ_{12}	0.597	2
Γ_{13}	0.570	3

Ranking: $\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$.

Taking the proposition 2 values and applying all the steps of the algorithm by using the equations (2), (6) - (13). By the closeness coefficient value, journal Γ_{10} is best of other journals.

6. Comparison

The figure 5 gives the graphical representation of the proposition 1, figure 6 gives the graphical representation of the proposition 2 and figure 7 gives the comparison of the propositions. The x – axis represents the four journals (alternative) and the y – axis represents distance values (according to the closeness coefficient value). The figure 7 says Journal 1 is the best of all other three journals under the TOPSIS method.

Figure 5. Geometric representation of proposition 1

Figure 6. Geometric representation of proposition 2

Figure 7. Comparison of the propositions

To address this, we have now included a comparative analysis of our proposed method with three well-established MCDM techniques: MULTIMOORA, AHP and VIKOR. All methods use the same expert weight assignments and decision matrix to ensure consistency and fairness in the comparison.

The final rankings of the alternatives across three propositions are shown in Table 19 below:

Table 19. Comparison with other methods

Method	Proposition	Ranking
Proposed method	Proposition 1	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$
	Proposition 2	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$
MULTIMOORA [17]	Proposition 1	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$
	Proposition 2	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11}$
VIKOR [16]	Proposition 1	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{11} > \Gamma_{12}$
	Proposition 2	$\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{11}$
AHP [21]	Proposition 1	$\Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{11}$
	Proposition 2	$\Gamma_{13} > \Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_{12} > \Gamma_{11}$

This comparative analysis demonstrates the robustness and stability of our proposed method. Notably, in two MCDM approaches, alternative Γ_{10} consistently emerges as the top-ranked option, reinforcing the reliability of the results. Moreover, the variations in the ranking of other alternatives across different methods emphasize that while each method follows distinct computational procedure, our approach maintains a high level of consistency and provides clear, justifiable rankings aligned with expert opinion and decision criteria. We believe this comparative analysis strengthens the validation of our proposed method and meets the expectations raised by the reviewer.

Comparison graph of the NSHSPIS & NSHSNIS

Figure 8. NSHSPIS & NSHSNIS for proposition 1

Figure 9. NSHSPIS & NSHSNIS for proposition 2

The above figure 8 & figure 9 gives the NSHSPIS and NSHSNIS for both propositions respectively.

7. Conclusion

This work offers a comprehensive and scalable approach to intelligent decision-making by uniting theoretical foundations of SHSSs with computational implementation and neutrosophic modeling. The

python-based construction of SHSS enables the automated generation of universal sets, sub-criteria power sets, and logical proposition mappings, bridging abstract mathematics with practical tools. Integrating NSHSS into the TOPSIS framework allows for realistic and hierarchical representation of criteria while effectively modeling uncertainty through neutrosophic logic. The computation of decision-maker weights further strengthens the model's capacity for fairness and transparency in group evaluations. Applied to the problem of Q1 journal selection, this integrated model demonstrates high adaptability and reliability. Through the application results, journal 1 (Γ_{10}) is the best journal among other three journals. Future extensions may involve hybridizing with other MCDM techniques like MULTIMOORA, AHP and VIKOR then applying the framework across different domains requiring nuanced and data-sensitive decision-making under uncertain environments.

References

1. Abdalla, M. E. M.; Uzair, A.; Ishtiaq, A.; Tahir, M.; Kamran, M. Algebraic Structures and Practical Implications of Interval-Valued Fermatean Neutrosophic Super HyperSoft Sets in Healthcare. *Spectrum of Operational Research* **2025**, 2(1), 199-218.
2. Abdel-Basset, M.; Manogaran, G.; Gamal, A.; Smarandache, F. A Group Decision Making Framework Based on Neutrosophic TOPSIS Approach for Smart Medical Device Selection. *Journal of Medical Systems* **2019**, 43, 1-13.
3. Ahsan, M.; Sarwar, M. A.; Lone, S. A.; Almutlak, S. A.; Anwer, S. Optimizing New Technology Implementation Through Fuzzy Hypersoft Set: A Framework Incorporating Entropy, Similarity Measure, and TOPSIS Techniques. *IEEE Access* **2023**, 11, 80680-80691.
4. Ajabnoor, N. Evaluation of Distributed Leadership in Education Using Neutrosophic HyperSoft Set. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2024**, 72(1), 17.
5. Amiri-Aref, M.; Javadian, N.; Kazemi, M. A New Fuzzy Positive and Negative Ideal Solution for Fuzzy TOPSIS. *WSEAS Transactions on Circuits and Systems* **2012**, 11(3), 92-103.
6. Ayala Ayala, L. R.; Hernández Ramos, E. L.; Contento Correa, S. A. Neutrosophic TOPSIS-OWA Framework for Evaluating Data Protection Strategies in Judicial Systems. *Journal of Fuzzy Extension and Applications* **2024**, 5(Special Issue), 1-11.
7. Behzadian, M.; Otaghsara, S. K.; Yazdani, M.; Ignatius, J. A State-of-the-art Survey of TOPSIS Applications. *Expert Systems with Applications* **2012**, 39(17), 13051-13069.
8. Biswas, P.; Pramanik, S.; Giri, B. C. TOPSIS method for Multi-Attribute Group Decision-Making under Single-Valued Neutrosophic Environment. *Neural Computing and Applications* **2016**, 27, 727-737.
9. Bobin, A.; Thangaraja, P.; Prathab, H.; Thayalan, S. Decision Making Using Cubic HyperSoft TOPSIS method. *Journal of applied mathematics & infomatics*, The Korean Society for Computational and Applied Mathematics **2013**, 41(5), 973-988.
10. Chen, J. Measuring the Efficiency of Competitive Sports Talent Cultivation in Universities through the Synergy of Sports and Education using SuperHyperSoft Set. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, 82, 84-107.
11. Dhanalakshmi, G.; Sandhiya, S. An Unbiased Comparison of the MOORA TOPSIS and WASPAS Methods within the MATLAB Programming Environment, Utilizing a Fuzzy HyperSoft Sets Framework. *Palestine Journal of Mathematics* **2025**, 14(Special Issue II), 79-93.
12. Fujita, T. Some Types of Hyperdecision-Making and Superhyperdecision-Making. In *Advancing Uncertain Combinatorics through Graphization, Hyperization, and Uncertainization: Fuzzy, Neutrosophic, Soft, Rough, and Beyond* **2025**, Chapter 3, 221.
13. Fujita, T. Superhypersoft HyperRough Set and Superhypersoft Superhyperrough Set. *Preprint* **2025**.(researchgate.net).

14. Hwang, C. L.; Yoon, K. Methods for Multiple Attribute Decision Making. Springer journal **1981**.
15. Jafar, M. N.; Saeed, M.; Saqlain, M.; Yang, M. S. Trigonometric Similarity Measures for Neutrosophic Hypersoft Sets With Application to Renewable Energy Source Selection. *IEEE Access* **2021**, *9*, 129178-129187.
16. Kamal, N. L. A. M.; Abdullah, L.; Yee, F. M.; Abdullah, I.; Vafaei, N. Single Valued Neutrosophic VIKOR and Its Application to Wastewater Treatment Selection. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2021**, *47*, 250-272.
17. Kara, K.; Yalçın, G. C.; Edinsel, S. Warehouse Manager Selection by CRITIC-MULTIMOORA Hybrid Method based on Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets. *Journal of Maritime Transport and Logistics* **2023**, *4*(1), 48-64.
18. Kaur, M.; Singh, A. Approach to Multi-Criteria Decision-Making in a Neutrosophic Picture Hyper-Soft Set Environment using Generalized Neutrosophic TOPSIS. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2024**, *67*(1), 5.
19. Liu, J. Application of the SuperHyperSoft Set for Comprehensive Teaching Quality Analysis in College English Translation Courses for Enhanced Learning Results. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, *82*, 443-457.
20. Maji, P. K. Neutrosophic Soft Set. *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics* **2013**, *5*(1), 157-168
21. Mohamed, F.; Shuhaizam, N. A. S. A.; Zaki, N. N. A. M.; ROSDI, N. A. M. Multi Criteria Decision Making under Single-Valued Neutrosophic Set Environment for Supplier Selection. *Journal of Quality Measurement and Analysis JQMA* **2024**, *20*(2), 149-162.
22. Molodtsov, D. Soft Set Theory—First Results. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications* **1999**, *37*(4-5), 19-31.
23. Nabeeh, N. A.; Smarandache, F.; Abdel-Basset, M.; El-Ghareeb, H. A.; Aboelfetouh, A. An Integrated Neutrosophic-TOPSIS Approach and Its Application to Personnel Selection: A New Trend in Brain Processing and Analysis. *IEEE Access* **2019**, *7*, 29734-29744.
24. Olson, D. L. Comparison of Weights in TOPSIS Models. *Mathematical and Computer Modelling* **2004**, *40*(7-8), 721-727.
25. Pramanik, S.; Dey, P. P.; Giri, B. C. TOPSIS for Single-Valued Neutrosophic Soft Expert Set Based Multi-Attribute Decision-Making Problems. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2015**, *10*, 88-95.
26. Ramasamy, R.; Shanmugavel, K.; Smarandache, F. Application of Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets in MADM. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, *85*(1), 35.
27. Riaz, M.; Naeem, K.; Zareef, I.; Afzal, D. Neutrosophic N-Soft Sets with TOPSIS Method for Multiple Attribute Decision Making. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2020**, *32*, 146-170.
28. Saeed, M.; Ahsan, M.; Siddique, M. K.; Ahmad, M. R. A Study of the Fundamentals of Hypersoft Set Theory.(pdf) researchgate.net **2020**,1-9.
29. Sajid, M.; Khan, K. A.; Rahman, A. U. Evaluation of Motorcycle Brands Using Multi-attribute Decision-Making Method Under Single-Valued Neutrosophic Cubic Hypersoft Set Environment. *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems* **2024**, *17*(1), 292.
30. Sajid, M.; Khan, K. A.; Frnda, J.; Rahman, A. U. A Novel Multi-Attribute Decision-Making Method for Supplier Selection in the Health Care Industry Using Cosine Similarity Measures of Single-Valued Neutrosophic Cubic Hypersoft Sets. *IEEE Access* **2025**, 13.
31. Sajid, M.; Khan, K. A.; Rahman, A. U.; Bajri, S. A.; Alburaikan, A.; Khalifa, H. A. E. W. A Novel Algorithmic Multi-Attribute Decision-Making Framework for Solar Panel Selection using Modified Aggregations of Cubic Intuitionistic Fuzzy Hypersoft Set. *Heliyon* **2024**, *10*(17).
32. Salama, A. A.; Alblowi, S. A. Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *IOSR Journal of Mathematics (IOSR-JM)* **2012**, *3*(4), 31-35
33. Saqlain, M.; Jafar, M. N.; Riaz, M. A New Approach of Neutrosophic Soft Set with Generalized Fuzzy TOPSIS in Application of Smartphone Selection. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2020**, *32*(1), 307-316.
34. Saqlain, M.; Kumam, P.; Kumam, W. Neutrosophic Linguistic valued Hypersoft Set with Application: Medical Diagnosis and Treatment. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2023**, *63*, 130-152.

35. Saqlain, M.; Riaz, M.; Saleem, M. A.; Yang, M. S. Distance and Similarity Measures for Neutrosophic Hypersoft Set (NHSS) with Construction of NHSS-TOPSIS and Applications. *IEEE Access* **2021**, *9*, 30803-30816.
36. Saqlain, M.; Saeed, M.; Ahmad, M. R.; Smarandache, F. Generalization of TOPSIS for Neutrosophic Hypersoft set using Accuracy Function and its Application. *Neutrosophic sets and systems* **2019**, *27*, 131-137.
37. Smarandache, F. A unifying field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic. In *Philosophy* **1999**, American Research Press, 1-141.
38. Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic Set—A Generalization of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* **2005**, *24(3)*, 287.
39. Smarandache, F. Extension of Soft Set to Hypersoft Set, and then to Plithogenic Hypersoft Set. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems: An International Book Series in Information Science and Engineering* **2018**, *22*, 168.
40. Smarandache, F. Foundation of the SuperHyperSoft Set and the Fuzzy Extension SuperHyperSoft Set: A New Vision. *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications* **2023**, *11*, 48-51.
41. Smarandache, F. New Types of Soft Sets: Hypersoft Set, Indeterminsoft Set, Indeterminhypersoft Set, and Treesoft set. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science (IJNS)* **2023**, *20(4)*, 58-64.
42. Smarandache, F.; Gayathri, P.; Karuppusamy, E.; Krishnaprakash, S.; Gomathi, S. Optimizing Electric Vehicle Selection Using Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Set Theory. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, *86*, 710-729.
43. Smarandache, F.; Saranya, A.; Kalavathi, A.; Krishnaprakash, S. Neutrosophic SuperHyperSoft Sets. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, *77*.
44. Sudha, S.; Priya, R.; Martin, N.; Broumi, S.; Smarandache, F. Combined Plithogenic Hypersoft Sets in Decision Making on Supplier Selection with Different MCDM Approaches. *Engineering Review* **2024**, *44(4-SI 2024)*, 122-140.
45. Tiwari, V.; Jain, P. K.; Tandon, P. An Integrated Shannon Entropy and TOPSIS for Product Design Concept Evaluation Based on Bijective Soft Set. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* **2019**, *30*, 1645-1658.
46. Zhang, D. SuperHyperSoft Framework for College English Blended Teaching Quality Evaluation in the New Era: Addressing Uncertainty and Complexity. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* **2025**, *80(1)*, 18.
47. Zulqarnain, R. M.; Abdal, S.; Maalik, A.; Ali, B.; Zafar, Z.; Ahamad, M. I.; Dayan, F. Application of TOPSIS Method in Decision Making via Soft Set. *Biomed J Sci Tech Res* **2020**, *24(3)*, 18208-18215.
48. Zulqarnain, R. M.; Siddique, I.; Ali, R.; Jarad, F.; Samad, A.; Abdeljawad, T. Neutrosophic Hypersoft Matrices with Application to Solve Multiattributive Decision-Making Problems. *Complexity* **2021**, *1*, 5589874.

Received: Feb 16, 2025. Accepted: Aug 11, 2025